

Detecting urban structure through inter-city human interactions in China

George Willis¹, Zhaoya Gong² and Emmanouil Tranos³

¹University of Birmingham

²University of Bristol and The Alan Turing Institute

February 12, 2021

Summary

We combine novel inter-city human interaction data with traditional node attribute data to explore how the Chinese urban network is structured, and how this is associated with the economic performance of cities in an increasingly urbanising China. We then employ well-established unsupervised machine learning algorithms to cluster the Chinese cities based on these network variables and create urban typologies based on mid-term migration patterns. We identify 7 clusters of cities with shared network characteristics and contrast their economic performances based on more traditional data. The most disconnected, peripheral cities are also shrinking with a negative population difference, but are not necessarily the weakest economically, with a reliance on primary industry.

KEYWORDS: Chinese cities, urban network, shrinking cities, population flow, clustering

1. Introduction

China has experienced unprecedented levels of urbanization. However, the rapid rise of Global cities such as Shanghai or Shenzhen is contrasted by a much bleaker picture for many smaller cities in China. The increasing role of globalisation has caused the inter-competition between cities to intensify, making it essential to understand the flow of goods and services between these cities. Often in the shadow of Global Cities, lie cities on the periphery of urban networks or even disconnected entirely. Their decreased capacity to attract or generate flows of goods and services, or geographic isolation means they are becoming increasingly cut off from wider urban networks. In previous urban network research, these cities are often forgotten or even completely removed from analysis as researchers tend to focus on the larger core of highly connected cities. However, for a better understanding of the process of urban growth and shrinkage the entire network needs to be considered. Across the world, researchers are getting to grips with the process of urban shrinkage and the complex set of factors that cause it. Deindustrialisation, resource depletion and inter-city competition are just some of the causes of out-migration and eventual population loss for some cities. The growing frequency of shrinking cities calls for a new perspective that places both growth and shrinkage side by side in research.

In order to understand the spatial patterns of growth and shrinkage, the way cities interact with each other need to be considered. The rise of the ‘Smart City’ has led to the creation of huge volumes of digital data about society in order to aid regional and urban planning. There are number of ways to measure these inter-city interactions from inter-firm links (Pan et al. 2017) and infrastructure (Yang et al. 2018), to human mobility (Lin, Wu, and Li 2019). However these studies are still often limited in their spatial or temporal scale, with many studies using the capacity of passenger flows, rather than actual flows (Feng et al. 2014; Mu and Yeh 2020). This paper fills this gap by utilising human mobility patterns to study the spatial patterns of inter-city flows in China. Specifically we utilise network analysis

¹ gcw519@bham.ac.uk

² Z.Gong@bham.ac.uk

³ e.tranos@bristol.ac.uk

Table 1- Descriptives of Network Variables

Measure	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Out-Degree	214.896	83.575	18.000	342.000
Strength Difference	318.973	61546.924	-383289.000	212436.000
Strength	897957.672	1180097.245	31306.000	9040906.000
Node Symmetry	0.021	0.101	-0.194	0.530
Pagerank	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.026
Authority Score	0.076	0.117	0.001	1.000
Hub Score	0.072	0.112	0.000	1.000
Average Flow Distance	1436.783	415.051	1026.723	3288.893

combined with unsupervised clustering to examine the spatial patterns of the inter-city interactions. Clustering methods have been used in complex networks to find agglomerations (Lin, Wu, and Li 2019b), hierarchies (Cullinane et al. 2012) and city typologies (Van et al. 2010). Diverse combinations of geographic locations, governance and historical past means that urban areas are extremely heterogeneous. This means urban systems can be extremely complex for researchers and governments alike, to address on a regional or global scale. We utilise clustering methods in order to characterise the Chinese Urban Network into patterns to aid our analysis.

2. Data and Methodology

In order to understand the inter-city human interactions we employ Baidu Map’s human flow data. Baidu Maps has over 350 million monthly users, and can be used to create geo-referenced datasets in China. Our data captures the movement of technology devices connected to Baidu Maps at the prefecture city level. Therefore this data represents the flow of people carrying these devices, from one city to another. Furthermore, this data is at a mid-term temporal level, meaning these devices stay in a city for a minimum three month period for the flow to count in our data. These seasonal flows of people are used to represent dominance of a city by capturing the number of people who stay there for a minimum three month period. This data is unique by identifying the meaningful trips rather than daily commutes, and also captures the real flow of people rather than estimates as seen in previous studies using train or bus timetables. A city with a high number of flows, will be dominant within the network, while those with very few flows will be disconnected and perhaps suffer from urban shrinkage. To compare the node attributes to the network analysis we will employ socio-economic variables for each prefecture level city, taken from provincial statistical yearbooks.

In order to establish the importance of each city based on these flows, we first adopt a network approach. This method quantifies the relationships between cities to create an urban hierarchy rather than using traditional node attributes (W. Yang et al. 2019). To assess each city, we use multiple centrality measures as shown in Table 1. The different measures allow us to compare how each city performs in different aspects of the network. For example Jon Kleinberg’s HITS algorithm are used to measure the role of each node within a network and measure, not only links to every city, but how well linked ‘hub’ cities are linked to ‘authority’ cities, while node symmetry measures the difference between the incoming and outgoing interactions for every node allowing to see if a city is primarily a destination or origin. The range of measures used above is then taken to assess the role of each city within the wider Chinese urban network. We do this by using K-means clustering on our measures in order to create a city typology, based on shared network characteristics. The final step is to understand how these city typologies differ, not just within the network, structurally. To do this, we employ multinomial regression with the socio-demographic variables and our created clusters.

3. The Chinese Urban Network

Figure 1- City clusters

In total, we identify 7 typologies from the unsupervised clustering. These are shown in Figure 1, along with the standardised network variables. As expected, the dominant cities, have their own clusters, however, as Figure 2 shows, they have been split into two distinct clusters (3 and 7). This, in part, is due to the polycentric nature of the Pearl River Delta. Shenzhen, Guangzhou, and Dongguan have been separated into their own cluster due to their dense connections with the rest of the network, which is not uncommon in previous research (Zhang et al. 2020). This is highlighted by Figure 2 which shows how similar these three cities are. The second dominant cluster contains 9 cities and is made up of major cities such as Beijing, Shanghai and Chongqing. These cities are the typical mega-cities of China, with huge populations, which will naturally cause the number of flows to increase. Importantly we also identify a peripheral city typology with fewer linkages within the network, as well as a group that is not peripheral but have weak connections to the network. This is shown in Figure 3, where the dominant cluster (7) have linkages to almost every city in the network, while Cluster 2 cities primarily stay within their provinces, particularly in the Northeast of China.

Figure 2- Overview of K-means using PCA

We then go one step further in comparing how these cities perform with regards to socio-economic data. We use multinomial regression in order to see how our chosen city typologies effect their socio-economic status. We take the cluster with medium sized cities within the network as our baseline cluster for our regression and see how the variables change for each cluster. The results are shown in Table 2. As suspected, the peripheral cities are also the cluster suffering from urban shrinkage. This process of shrinking is then exacerbated by the outflow of capital and goods, as they are directed towards the core. By being on the periphery, these cities are inevitably most vulnerable to the mobility of labour and capital when competing against mega-cities. Li and Mykhnenko (2018) suggest, a major cause of urban shrinkage is deindustrialisation, as these cities struggle to adapt to a rapidly growing China. Therefore these cities are often mining or resource depleted areas, inevitably making them more vulnerable to deindustrialisation (Li and Zhang 2012). The combination of peripheral location, deindustrialisation and outflows leads to a shrinking population. Conversely, the best performing cities with both the highest flows and highest GDP per capita have the highest tertiary sectors, as the focus shifts towards these industries. Further insights can be gained in studying individual patterns between cities rather than the network as a whole to understand the dynamic relationships between competing cities.

Figure 3- Significant flows a) Peripheral city Flows (Cluster 5) b) Mega-city Flows (Cluster 7)

Table 2- Multinomial Regression Results

	Dependent variable:					
	Weak but close (1)	Pearl River Delta (2)	Regional Dominant (3)	Peripheral Cities (4)	Medium Central (5)	Mega-Cities (6)
Total population	-7.704*** (1.524)	-28.608 (69.156)	3.433*** (0.833)	-8.026*** (2.389)	0.815 (0.607)	4.404*** (1.326)
Population Difference	1.099* (0.570)	-11.987 (190.949)	0.422 (0.575)	-3.372*** (0.880)	-0.197 (0.407)	0.537 (1.088)
Weighted Flows	-4.059*** (1.163)	7.655 (22.343)	2.471*** (0.618)	1.286 (0.986)	1.607*** (0.570)	3.430*** (0.768)
Population Density	0.138 (0.705)	23.002* (13.959)	1.038 (0.713)	-11.732*** (3.392)	-0.879 (0.575)	0.464 (1.249)
GDP (100 million Yuan)	-5.275** (2.197)	12.796 (9.767)	1.636 (1.012)	-0.098 (1.419)	-2.145** (0.883)	4.373*** (1.060)
Primary GDP	2.475*** (0.828)	24.258 (78.897)	-0.502 (0.601)	2.809*** (1.040)	0.569 (0.457)	-1.038 (1.078)
Secondary GDP	-3.623 (2.756)	-7.723 (88.801)	-3.388** (1.616)	-7.530*** (2.813)	-0.341 (1.352)	-2.622 (1.905)
Tertiary GDP	-6.060 (4.424)	22.193 (55.362)	7.135*** (2.343)	3.903 (3.205)	-2.697 (1.950)	5.237** (2.431)
Constant	-9.288*** (1.906)	-63.242 (83.854)	-1.742*** (0.544)	-12.220*** (2.123)	-1.373*** (0.485)	-8.315*** (2.313)
Nagelkerke R2	0.8945	0.8945	0.8945	0.8945	0.8945	0.8945
Akaike Inf. Crit.	495.179	495.179	495.179	495.179	495.179	495.179

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

References

- Cullinane, Kevin, and Yuhong Wang. 2012. "The Hierarchical Configuration of the Container Port Industry: An Application of Multiple Linkage Analysis." *Maritime Policy & Management* 39 (2): 169–87.
- Feng, CC, D Xie, X Ma, and LL Cai Sinica. 2014. "Functional polycentricity of the urban region in the Zhujiang River Delta based on intercity rail traffic flow." *Scientia Geographica*.
- Li, He, and Vlad Mykhnenko. 2018. "Urban shrinkage with Chinese characteristics." *The Geographical Journal* 184 (4): 398–412. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12266>.
- Li, He, and Ping-yu Zhang. 2012. "Main Characteristics and Driving Factors of Industry Structure Evolution in Northeast China Since 1990." *Arid Land Geography* 35: 829–37.
- Lin, Jinyao, Zhifeng Wu, and Xia Li. 2019a. "Measuring inter-city connectivity in an urban agglomeration based on multi-source data." *International Journal of Geographical Information Science* 33 (5): 1062–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2018.1563302>.
- Mu, Xiaoyan, and Anthony Gar-On Yeh. 2020. "Regional Delineation of China Based on Commuting Flows." *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space* 52 (3): 478–82.
- Pan, Fenghua, Wenkai Bi, James Lenzer, and Simon Zhao. 2017. "Mapping urban networks through inter-firm service relationships: The case of China." *Urban Studies Journal Limited* 54 (16): 3639–54. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098016685511>.

Van Nuffel, Nathalie, Ben Derudder, and Frank Witlox. 2010. "Even Important Connections Are Not Always Meaningful: On the Use of a Polarisation Measure in a Typology of European Cities in Air Transport Networks." *Tijdschrift Voor Economische En Sociale Geografie* 101 (3): 333–48.

Yang, Haoran, Martin Dijst, Patrick Witte, Hans Van Ginkel, and Weiling Yang. 2018. "The Spatial Structure of High Speed Railways and Urban Networks in China: A Flow Approach." *Tijdschrift Voor Economische En Sociale Geografie* 109 (1): 109–28. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tesg.12269>.

Yang, Wei, Xiang Yu, Dian Wang, Jinrui Yang, and Ben Zhang. 2019. "Spatio-Temporal Evolution of Technology Flows in China: Patent Licensing Networks 2000–2017." *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 1–30.

Zhang, Pingyu. 2008. "Revitalizing Old Industrial Base of Northeast China: Process, Policy and Challenge." *Chinese Geographical Science* 18 (2): 109–18.

Zhang, Wenjia, Chenyu Fang, Lin Zhou, and Jiancheng Zhu. 2020. "Measuring Megaregional Structure in the Pearl River Delta by Mobile Phone Signaling Data: A Complex Network Approach." *Cities* 104: 102809.